

RELIABILITY OF UNCERTAIN FLEXIBLE LAMINATED PLATE
UNDER RANDOM IN-PLANE LOADS

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ABSTRACT

A geometrically nonlinear stochastic thin plate finite element is formulated to study the reliability of fiber reinforced laminated plates with structural uncertainties under random in-plane loads. The stochastic solution procedure is developed based on the mean-centered second-order perturbation technique together with the Newton-Raphson iterative method. First order reliability methods are adopted to derive safety index. To demonstrate the applicability of the present developments, a series of fracture and postbuckling analyses of thin plates with structural uncertainties under random in-plane loads are performed. The results quantify the effects of these uncertain parameters on the reliability of the example laminated plates under in-plane loads. The results also show the capability of the current method in analyzing and designing the laminated structures with uncertain parameters subjected to random loads.

KEYWORDS: Failure criterion; Finite element analysis; Plates; Postbuckling; Reliability.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the stochastic finite element method (SFEM) has been widely used to study the effects of material, geometrical and loading uncertainties on the structural behaviors. The method is developed based on the mean-centered second-order perturbation technique and has been proven to be quite effective and accurate for analyzing structures with small property fluctuations. For examples, Handa and Anderson [1] solved the linear static response of beams and trusses with uncertain material properties under random loads. The expectations and variances of deflection and stress of boron-epoxy laminated plate with random lamina angle orientations and thicknesses under compression were studied by Tani, et al. [2]. Recently, the SFEM has been extended to solve the nonlinear problems. Liu, et al. [3] proposed a probabilistic finite element method to analyze the static and dynamic response of elastic-plastic beams and plates with uncertain material properties and uncertain yielding stress subjected to random loads.

The aboved-mentioned results have demonstrated that the SFEM is useful in predicting means and variances of uncertain responses. Such second moment statistical information can provide insight into the effects of uncertain parameters on structural behavior. However, the information alone is not adequate for reliability analysis, since most engineering structures

are designed with high degree of reliability, which can not be well described by the first two moments. Calculation of structural reliability can be achieved by first filtering the uncertain structural response calculated by SFEM and the statistic properties of the random variables through the failure criteria assumed, and then performing the numerical evaluation of the probability of failure events. The calculation can be difficult to perform if the number of non-normally distributed random variables exceed two, or the failure function becomes nonlinear. Several algorithms have been developed to handle such difficulty. Among them, Rackwitz and Fiessler [4] proposed a first order reliability method (FORM) which calculated the safety index through approximating the nonlinear limit state surface by a tangent hyperplane and transforming the non-normally distributed random variables to equivalent normally distributed ones. The sensitivity and importance measures of individual stochastic variables in structural reliability have been discussed by, among the other, Hohenbichler and Rackwitz [5]. They demonstrated that the random variable with absolutely large alpha-value was considered to be stochastically important comparing to the random variables with absolutely small alpha-values.

The implementation of SFEM together with FORM or SORM for the reliability analysis of complex structures has been progressed steadily but mainly dealing with linear problems. For examples, the reliability of linear uncertain beam-frame structure subjected to random loads was calculated by Hisada and Nakagiri [6]. Studies of reliability of laminate plate with uncertain material parameters were reported by Tani, et al. [7]. using strength failure criteria.

The objective of this study is to formulate a geometrically nonlinear stochastic thin plate finite element to study the reliability of fiber reinforced laminated thin plates with structural uncertainties under random in-plane loads. The structural uncertainties considered include modulus of elasticity, Poisson's ratio, thickness, fiber orientation of individual lamina, as well as the geometric imperfection of the plate. The uncertainties are assumed to be space-wise fully correlated through out the lamina. The stochastic solution procedure is developed based on the mean-centered second-order perturbation together with Newton-Raphson iterative method. The Hill-Tsai failure criterion for the unidirectional lamina and a displacement criterion for the plate are used to set up the limit state function. Rackwitz-Fiessler FORM is adopted to derive the safety index. Three examples are illustrated and discussed to validate the present developments. The reliabilities of a three-layer angle-ply linear laminated constant plane stress plate with random material properties are first calculated to demonstrate the accuracy of the FORM. Two postbuckling examples including a simply supported isotropic plate and a simply supported two-layer cross-ply laminated plate with uncertain material properties and geometric imperfections under random in-plane loads are then studied. The stochastic importance of each individual random variable is discussed quantitatively through the alpha-value calculated. The results quantify the effects of these uncertain parameters on the reliability of the plates considered. The results also show the capability of the current method in analyzing and designing the laminated structures with uncertain parameters subjected to random loads.

2. FORMULATION

A 48 d.o.f. skewed quadrilateral deterministic thin shell finite element including the effect of geometrical nonlinearity previously developed by Yang and Wu [8] is extended here to formulate a geometrically nonlinear stochastic finite element. The element has 12 degrees of freedom at each of the four corner nodes: $u, u_x, u_y, u_{xy}, v, v_x, v_y, v_{xy}, w, w_x, w_y, w_{xy}$, where u, v and w are the displacements in the nodal local coordinate system.

2.1 Strain-Displacement Relations The strain-displacement relations for the imperfect plates are represented in terms of local coordinate components which are an extended version of the strain-displacement relations given in tensorial form by Mason [9]. The effects of

imperfections are included by modifying the tangential strain-displacement relations. These are given as

$$\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{a}_\alpha \bullet \mathbf{u}_{,\beta} + \mathbf{a}_\beta \bullet \mathbf{u}_{,\alpha} + \mathbf{u}_{,\alpha} \bullet \mathbf{u}_{,\beta} + \mathbf{u}_{,\alpha} \bullet \mathbf{s}_{,\beta} + \mathbf{u}_{,\beta} \bullet \mathbf{s}_{,\alpha}) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{a}_α , \mathbf{u} , and \mathbf{s} are the base vectors of the middle surface, displacement vector, and imperfection vector at a given point on the plate surface with reference to nodal point local coordinate system, respectively; α and β vary from 1 to 2.

2.2 Laminated Constitutive Relations The laminated anisotropic construction of the plate is assumed to be made up of n layers. Each lamina is assumed to be orthotropic with its principal material axes at an angle with the local coordinate axes. The stress-strain relation for each layer is expressed with reference to the local coordinate system through coordinate transformation. The stress and moment resultants are then related to the middle surface strain ϵ and the change of curvature κ [8]

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $\{\mathbf{N}\}$ is the vector of resultant tangential forces, $\{\mathbf{M}\}$ is the vector of resultant moments, and the coefficients in matrices $[\mathbf{A}]$, $[\mathbf{B}]$ and $[\mathbf{D}]$ are given as

$$[\mathbf{A}_{ij}, \mathbf{B}_{ij}, \mathbf{D}_{ij}] = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \mathbf{Q}_{ij}(1, z, z^2) dz \quad (i, j=1, 2, 6) \quad (3)$$

with \mathbf{Q}_{ij} denoting the plane-stress stiffness for individual layer and t the total thickness of the plate.

2.3 Stochastic Finite Element Method The random field of a single uncertain parameter considered in this study is assumed to be space-wise fully correlated through out the lamina. The random amplitude ξ_i of the parameter can be expressed as the sum of its mean value $\langle \xi_i \rangle$ and a random variable x_i as

$$\xi_i = \langle \xi_i \rangle + x_i \quad (4)$$

The mean value of random variable x_i is equal to zero, thus it has the same standard deviation as ξ_i . The equilibrium equations for the geometrically nonlinear stochastic finite element model can be written as

$$\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{P} is the internal force vector, \mathbf{F} is the external force vector, and \mathbf{x} is the random parameter vector which may include random laminate fiber orientation, modulus of elasticity, Poisson's ratio, thickness, geometric imperfection of the plates, or uncertain random loads. Expanding \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{F} , and \mathbf{u} based on Taylor series with respect to \mathbf{x} and retaining up to second order terms yield,

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{u}_{x_i} x_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbf{u}_{x_i x_j} x_i x_j \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{F}_{x_i} x_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbf{F}_{x_i x_j} x_i x_j \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P} &= \mathbf{P}_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{P}_u \mathbf{u}_{x_i} + \mathbf{P}_{x_i}) x_i \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (\mathbf{P}_{uu} \mathbf{u}_{x_i} \mathbf{u}_{x_j} + \mathbf{P}_{u x_i} \mathbf{u}_{x_j} + \mathbf{P}_{u x_j} \mathbf{u}_{x_i} + \mathbf{P}_u \mathbf{u}_{x_i x_j} + \mathbf{P}_{x_i x_j}) x_i x_j \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The symbol N denotes the total number of random variables. Substituting Eqs. 6-8 into Eq. 5, the 0th, 1st, and 2nd order equations are found in terms of the random displacement vector as,

$$\mathbf{P}_o = \mathbf{F}_o \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_u \mathbf{u}_{x_i} = \mathbf{F}_{x_i} - \mathbf{P}_{x_i} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_u \mathbf{u}_{x_i x_j} = \mathbf{F}_{x_i x_j} - \mathbf{P}_{uu} \mathbf{u}_{x_i} \mathbf{u}_{x_j} - \mathbf{P}_{ux_i} \mathbf{u}_{x_j} - \mathbf{P}_{ux_j} \mathbf{u}_{x_i} - \mathbf{P}_{x_i x_j} \quad (11)$$

Equation 9 is a nonlinear one involving \mathbf{u}_o up to the third order. It can be solved by a standard linear incremental approach in combination with the Newton-Raphson iterative method [8]. Equations 10 and 11 are linear in \mathbf{u}_{x_i} and $\mathbf{u}_{x_i x_j}$, respectively. They can be solved by substituting \mathbf{u}_o into \mathbf{P}_u in Eqs. 10 and 11 and then moving the inverse of \mathbf{P}_u to the right hand side of the equations. After the random displacement vector is calculated, the random stresses in the k^{th} layer can be derived as,

$$\sigma_{12}^k(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{x})^k \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x})^k (\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}) + z^k \kappa(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x})) \quad (12)$$

where σ_{12}^k represents the stresses in the material principal direction, \mathbf{T}^k the coordinate transformation matrix, z^k the vertical distance between middle surface and center of k^{th} layer. The 0th, 1st, and 2nd order stress vectors can be found by expanding Eq. 12 using Taylor series with respect to \mathbf{x} as shown in Eqs. 6-8.

2.4 First Order Reliability Method The random displacement and random stress vectors obtained in the previous section can be incorporated into the first order reliability method to derive safety index β and probability of failure P_f . The probability of failure is defined as

$$P_f = P \left[g(\mathbf{x}) < 0 \right] = \int_{\Omega} f(\mathbf{x}) dx \quad (13)$$

where $f(\mathbf{x})$ is the joint probability density function of \mathbf{x} , Ω is the failure region, and $g(\mathbf{x})$ is the so-called limit state function which separate the design space into failure ($g(\mathbf{x}) < 0$) and safe ($g(\mathbf{x}) > 0$) regions. Two types of limit state functions are considered in this study. The first one concerns the nodal displacement at a designated point exceeding an allowable value u_{cr} ,

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = u_{cr} - u(\mathbf{x}) \quad (14)$$

The second performance function is constructed at the lamina level using random lamina stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , τ_{12} and random lamina strengths X , Y , S through Hill-Tsai criterion,

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{X^2} \right) - \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S} \right)^2 \quad (15)$$

To calculate P_f using FORM, the non-normally distributed random vector \mathbf{x} is first transformed to N independent, standard normal random variables Z_i as

$$Z_i = \frac{x_i - \mu_{x_i}}{\sigma_{x_i}} \quad (16)$$

where μ_{x_i} , σ_{x_i} are the mean value and standard deviation of x_i , respectively. The idea of deriving P_f using FORM is to find the minimum distance β (safety index) between the origin and the limit state surface $G = [Z_i; g(\mathbf{Z}) = 0]$ in the standard normal domain. By assuming that there is only one minimum distance point \mathbf{Z}^* on the limit state surface G , the limit state function $g(\mathbf{Z})$ can be expanded by its first order Taylor series at \mathbf{Z}^* ,

$$g(\mathbf{Z}) = \nabla g(\mathbf{Z}^*)^T (\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{Z}^*) \quad (17)$$

where $\nabla g(\mathbf{Z}^*)$ denotes the gradient of the function $g(\mathbf{Z})$ at \mathbf{Z}^* , the safety index β is found by letting

$$\mathbf{Z}^* = \beta \alpha \quad (18)$$

$$|\alpha| = 1 \quad (19)$$

The α is called the alpha-value vector. The i^{th} component of α can be interpreted as the importance measure for the corresponding random variable x_i . The random variable with absolutely large alpha-value is considered to be stochastically important comparing to those with absolutely small alpha-values. The safety index β described in Eqs. 17-19 can be solved by Rackwitz-Fiessler iterative scheme [4]. The probability of failure P_f is then derived as

$$P_f = \Phi(-\beta) \quad (20)$$

where Φ is the standard normal distribution function.

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

3.1 Linear Three-layer Angle-Ply Constant Plane Stress Laminated Plate with Uncertain Material Properties Subjected to Uncertain Multiaxial Loads

The reliability of three-layer angle-ply constant plane stress glass-epoxy laminated plate [15/-15/15] with uncertain material properties subjected to uncertain multiaxial loads was studied to verify to accuracy of the Rackwitz-Fiessler first order reliability method. The state of stresses within a single lamina was assumed to be constant and can be derived directly from Eqs. 2, 3 and 12. The expected values of the lamina material properties were assumed as $E_1=29.96$ GPa (4.34×10^6 psi), $E_2=8.45$ GPa (1.23×10^6 psi), $G_{12}=4.0$ GPa (0.58×10^6 psi), $\nu_{12}=0.32$. The expected value of the lamina thickness h was assumed as 1.27×10^{-4} m (0.005 in). The COV's for E_1 , G_{12} , h , and loadings σ_x , σ_y were all assumed to be 5%. The STD's of the lamina angle orientations θ were assumed to be 2° . The random variables E_1 , G_{12} , h , σ_x , σ_y , and θ were all assumed to be normally distributed. It was further assumed that E_1 , G_{12} , h , and θ were fully correlated among the three laminae. The failure criterion used in this example is based on that suggested by Yamada and Sun [10] which is a degenerated form of Hill-Tsai criterion (Eq. 15) with $\sigma_2=0$. The lamina strengths X and S were assumed to be Weibull distributed with two-parameter distribution functions of the form

$$F(X) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{X}{m}\right)^a} \quad (21)$$

where a and m are the shape and scale parameters, respectively. The shape and scale parameters for X and S were assumed to be $a_X=20.5$, $a_S=17.65$, and $m_X=0.876$ GPa (1.27×10^5 psi), $m_S=0.054$ GPa (7.83×10^3 psi). The mean values of X and S were 0.848 GPa (1.23×10^5 psi) and 0.051 GPa (7.45×10^3 psi), respectively.

Seven different cases were studied for two loadings, one in x (σ_x) and one in y (σ_y) directions, respectively. For the first five cases, one of the five variables $\{E_1, G_{12}, h, \theta, \text{ or } \sigma_x (\sigma_y)\}$ was assumed random, the rest of the four variables and strengths X, S were kept as deterministic. For the sixth case, the strengths X and S were assumed random with zero correlation between them, the five variables were kept as deterministic. For the last case, all five variables and strengths X, S were assumed random with zero correlation among them.

The results of the safety index β for the seven cases subjected to loadings in x and y directions were plotted in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. Alternative results using Monte Carlo simulation method with 50,000 samples were also shown. Good agreement between the two results is observed. It is seen that for the seven cases studied, the case with zero correlation among the seven random variables produces the lowest reliability curve for both loading in x and y directions. Furthermore, for the loading in x direction (Fig. 1), the curve with only one random variable G_{12} shows the highest reliability. Within the range of loading $\langle \sigma_x \rangle$ between 138 MPa (2.0×10^4 psi) and 241 MPa (3.5×10^4 psi), the reliability curve with two random variables X and S is the closest to that of the one with zero correlation among all

uncertainties. For the loading in y direction (Fig. 2), the curve with only one random variable E_1 shows the highest reliability. The curve with random variable θ is the closest to that of the one with zero correlation among all uncertainties.

Figures 3 and 4 show the alpha-value of the seven random variables considered in the zero correlation case for loadings in the x and y directions, respectively. An attempt was made to arrange the random parameters in order of their overall significance, i.e., $S, \theta, h, \sigma_x, E_1, G_{12}, X$ in x direction and $\theta, S, h, \sigma_y, G_{12}, E_1, X$ in y direction, respectively. For the presently assumed mean values, COV's, and STD's, it is seen in Fig. 3 that, as the loading in x direction $\langle\sigma_x\rangle$ increases from 138 MPa to 310 MPa, the alpha-value decreases from 0.91 to 0.40 for variable S and increases from 0.35 to 0.74 for variable θ . The alpha-value increases from 0.16 to 0.34 for h , from 0.14 to 0.34 for σ_x and from 0.11 to 0.24 for E_1 . The alpha values for G_{12} and X remain insignificantly low. It is seen in Fig. 4, that as the loading in y direction $\langle\sigma_y\rangle$ increases from 7 MPa to 21 MPa, the alpha-value increases from 0.78 to 0.86 for variable θ , and decreases from 0.61 to 0.34 for variable S . The alpha-value increases slightly from 0.11 to 0.26 for variable h and from 0.10 to 0.26 for variable σ_y . The alpha-values for $G_{12}, E_1,$ and X remain insignificantly low. For the present two cases, the random variables S and θ are stochastically more critical than other variables in both loading in x and y directions. Of course, different assumption of the random variable values may alter this observation.

Figure 5 shows the contours of the safety index of the plate with zero correlation among the random variables $E_1, G_{12}, h, \theta, \sigma_x, \sigma_y,$ and X, S . The mean loadings were increased from -552 MPa (-8×10^4 psi) to 552 MPa (8×10^4 psi) in x direction and -41 MPa (-6×10^3 psi) to 41 MPa (6×10^3 psi) in y direction. The figure shows that the range enclosed by the two allowable loads shrinks as β value increases (the probability of failure decreases). Construction of such contour may be useful to the design of more reliable structure.

3.2 Postbuckling of an Isotropic Simply Supported Square Plate with Uncertain Material Properties and Geometric Imperfection Subjected to Random In-Plane Loads The example was to study the postbuckling behavior for an isotropic simply supported square plate. During the postbuckling movement, two loading edges were assumed to remain straight and other two edges stress-free. The length L of the plate was assumed to be deterministic with value 0.3 m (11.8 in). The mean value $\langle v \rangle$ and coefficient of variation $COV(v)$ of the material properties of the plate were assumed to be normally-distributed with values, $\langle E \rangle = 68.95$ GPa (10×10^6 psi), $COV(E) = 0.05$; $\langle v \rangle = 0.3333$, $COV(v) = 0.05$; $\langle h \rangle = 1.27 \times 10^{-3}$ m (0.05 in), $COV(h) = 0.025$. The shape of the geometric imperfection was assumed the same as the critical buckling mode with the following form

$$w_i(x, y) = |\mu| \langle h \rangle \sin \frac{\pi x}{L} \sin \frac{\pi y}{L} \quad (22)$$

where μ is the nondimensionalized amplitude of the imperfection with $\langle \mu \rangle = 0.0$, $STD = 0.05 \langle h \rangle$. The loading N_x was assumed to be normally-distributed with $COV(N_x) = 0.05$.

The plate with deterministic properties subjected to deterministic in-plane load was first calculated to test the accuracy of the present geometrically nonlinear finite element formulation. Four elements were used to model a quarter of the plate. The results for nondimensionalized total center deflection are plotted in Fig. 6 against nondimensionalized in-plane load for two cases, $\mu = 0.0$ and 0.1. Alternative solution calculated by Yamaki [11] using double Fourier series expansion is also plotted. Good agreement is seen between the two results.

The reliability of the plate with random properties and imperfection subjected to uncertain in-plane loads was calculated based on the displacement criterion (Eq. 14). The critical value of the displacement u_{cr} was assumed to be at the center with magnitude $2.0 \langle h \rangle$. Six different

cases were considered. For the first five cases, one of the five random variables (E , h , N_x , μ , or ν) was assumed random while the other four were assumed deterministic. For the last case, all the five random variables were assumed random with zero correlation among them. The results of the safety index β for these six cases were plotted in Fig. 7. It is seen that the curve with zero correlation among the five variables shows the lowest reliability, while the curve with random variable ν gives the highest reliability. Figure 8 shows the alpha-value of the five random variables considered in the zero correlation case. For the presently assumed mean values, COV's, and STD's, it is seen that as the nondimensional compressive loading $\langle N_x \rangle / N_{cr}$ increases from 12 to 18, the alpha-values for random variables E , h , and N_x are relatively the highest, in the neighborhood of 0.50 to 0.60. The alpha-values are considerably lower for μ and even more so for ν . Thus for the presently assumed parameter values, the random variables E , h , and N_x are found to be stochastically more critical than the variables μ and ν .

3.3 Postbuckling of a Two-Layer Cross-Ply [0/90] Laminated Simply Supported Square Plate with Uncertain Material Properties and Uncertain Geometric Imperfection Subjected to Random In-plane Load

The last example was to study the postbuckling behavior of a two-layer cross-ply [0/90] graphite-epoxy laminated simply supported square plate. During the postbuckling movement, all four edges were assumed as stress-free. The length L of the plate was assumed to be deterministic with value 0.254 m (10 in). The lamina properties were assumed as $\langle E_1 \rangle = 206.85$ GPa (30×10^6 psi), $\text{COV}(E_1) = 0.05$; $\langle E_2 \rangle = 5.17$ GPa (0.75×10^6 psi), $\text{COV}(E_2) = 0.0$; $\langle \nu_{12} \rangle = 0.25$, $\text{COV}(\nu_{12}) = 0.0$; $\langle G_{12} \rangle = 2.586$ GPa (0.375×10^6 psi), $\text{COV}(G_{12}) = 0.0$; $\langle h \rangle = 1.27 \times 10^{-4}$ m (0.005 in), $\text{COV}(h) = 0.05$. These properties were assumed to be normally-distributed and fully correlated among the two layers. The mean values of the two lamina angle orientations were assumed as 0° and 90° , respectively. The standard deviations were assumed to be 2° . The shape of the geometric imperfection was also assumed the same as that defined in Eq. 22, where the nondimensionalized imperfect amplitude μ was assumed normally-distributed with mean=0.0, $\text{STD}=0.1 \langle h \rangle$. The loading N_x was assumed to be normally-distributed with $\text{COV}(N_x) = 0.05$.

The postbuckling response of the laminated plate with deterministic properties subjected to deterministic load was first calculated using 4 elements for a quarter of the plate. The results for the total nondimensionalized center deflection with respect to nondimensionalized load were plotted in Fig. 9 with $\mu = 0.0, 0.1$ and 0.25 . Alternative solution calculated by Prabhakara [12] with $\mu = 0.0$ is also shown in the figure. Good agreement is observed between the two results.

The reliability of the plate with random properties and imperfection subjected to uncertain in-plane loads was calculated based on the same failure criterion as in example 3 with u_{cr} equals two times of the total thickness of the plate. Six different cases were considered. For the first five cases, one of the five variables (E_1 , h , θ , N_x , or μ) was assumed random while the other four were assumed to be deterministic. For the last case, all five variables were assumed random with zero correlation among them. The results of the safety index β for the six cases were plotted in Fig. 10. It is seen that, the case with all five variables random yields the lowest reliability curve. Also, when considering the individual effect of only one variable on the reliability of the plate, the random variable h produces the lowest curve. Figure 11 shows the alpha-value of the five random variables considered in the zero correlation case. For the presently assumed mean values, COV's, and STD's, it is seen that, as the nondimensional compressive loading $\langle N_x \rangle L^2 / E_2 \langle h \rangle^3$ increases from 8 to 18, the alpha-value decreases slightly from 0.96 to 0.88 for variable h , from 0.22 to 0.11 for variable μ , and increases from 0.15 to 0.42 for variable N_x , from 0.09 to 0.20 for variable E_1 . The alpha-value for θ remains insignificantly low. Thus for the presently assumed parameter values, the random variable h is found to be stochastically more critical than the other four variables E_1 , θ , N_x , and μ .

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A 48 d.o.f. geometrically nonlinear stochastic thin plate finite element has been formulated to study the reliability of fiber reinforced laminated plate with uncertain modulus of elasticity, Poisson's ratio, thickness, fiber orientation of individual lamina and geometric imperfection subjected to random in-plane loads. The stochastic solution procedure has been developed based on the mean-centered second-order perturbation technique together with Newton-Raphson iterative method. The Hill-Tsai failure criterion for the unidirectional lamina and a displacement criterion for the plate have been used to set up the limit state function. Rackwitz-Fiessler first order reliability method has been adopted to derive the safety index. In this study, range of values for each random parameters have been assumed and the results demonstrate the individual effect of these parameters on the reliability of the cases studied. The calculation of alpha-value further quantify the stochastic importance of these parameters. Such quantified information may be helpful in the design of more reliable laminated composite plate structures.

Acknowledgement This study was sponsored by the National Science Foundation through grant ECE-8516915. Technical guidance from S.C. Liu is acknowledged.

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Fig. 1: Safety index β of an angle-ply laminated plate [15/-15/15] with random material properties ($\theta, E_1, h, G_{12}, X, S$) subjected to random load (σ_x) in x direction

Fig. 2: Safety index β of an angle-ply laminated plate [15/-15/15] with random material properties ($\theta, E_1, h, G_{12}, X, S$) subjected to random load (σ_y) in y direction

Fig. 3: Alpha-value of random variables considered in Fig.1 with zero correlation among all uncertainties

Fig. 4: Alpha-value of random variables considered in Fig.2 with zero correlation among all uncertainties

Fig. 5: Contours of safety index of the angle-ply laminated plate [15/-15/15] with random material properties subjected to multi-axial random loads

Fig. 6: Postbuckling of an isotropic imperfect simply supported deterministic square plate with two loading edges kept straight and other two edges stress-free

Fig. 9: Postbuckling of a cross-ply laminated imperfect simply supported deterministic square plate [0/90]

Fig. 7: Safety index β of an isotropic plate with random material properties subjected to uni-axial random load

Fig. 10: Safety index β of a cross-ply laminated plate [0/90] with random material properties subjected to uni-axial random load

Fig. 8: Alpha-value of random variables considered in Fig.7 with zero correlation among all uncertainties

Fig. 11: Alpha-value of random variables considered in Fig.10 with zero correlation among all uncertainties